

EYE ON THE EARTH

Environmental Science from Space

•FOREWORD.

The mission of the UK Natural Environment Research Council is to advance understanding of the natural environment and the processes of environmental change, and to predict future change. A key strength of NERC is the ability to support multi-disciplinary research and to promote an integrated approach to study of all aspects of our natural environment. Earth observation is already a major technology assisting our understanding of natural processes and is set to become increasingly important with future space developments. The unique ability of artificial satellites to study processes in the Earth's oceans, on the land surface and in the atmosphere and the interactions between them, will ensure their continued contribution to our understanding of the Earth as a system. The current concerns about our environment and its future can only be addressed by an understanding of these basic natural processes, transcending national boundaries. In addition, many of these concerns are such that they require a global perspective - which is provided for us by Earth observation systems.

We are at the start of the most important period of research in the study of the Earth from space. We have recently seen the launch of ERS-1, the first of a series of European remote sensing satellites planned in the coming decade. There has never been so exciting a time for environmental science, nor a time when the information and understanding of the Earth which science provides is so vital. The information provided by Earth observation will help environmental science rise to this challenge

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Chairman
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•INTRODUCTION.

Survival of mankind depends on learning to live in harmony with the environment. Man's activities are not only causing damage to the environment but are also capable of influencing the system of the planet itself. It is important to understand the processes of change, where changes might be predicted and, where appropriate, prevented, contained or reversed.

Science has a crucial role to play in understanding the processes of environmental change and in deciding how mankind can best understand and manage the Earth and its resources. The UK Natural Environment Research Council is responsible for conducting research on all aspects of the environment, ranging from the solid Earth to ocean circulation, tropospheric chemistry to freshwater and marine biology, local to continental-scale hydrological processes and tropical biodiversity to polar ecology. This range of expertise allows all facets of environmental problems to be addressed, a factor which is increasingly important as we better understand the interactions between different components of the Earth as a system. It is, for example, vital in understanding the carbon cycle to consider sources and sinks of carbon in the oceans, together with their terrestrial counterparts, and the transport and interaction mechanisms between them.

Earth observation plays a key role in understanding processes on a global scale in all areas of the natural environment. For example, data from radar altimetry and thermal imaging of the ocean surface can be linked to models of circulation to improve our understanding of heat and momentum transport in the oceans. Such data are available simultaneously for the first time from the European Remote Sensing satellite, ERS-1, and are now being fed into modelling programmes at NERC institutes and university groups to provide more detailed understanding of the behaviour of the Earth's oceans. This work is a key element of the UK's contribution to the World Ocean Circulation

Experiment (WOCE). Programmes are also underway which consider the biology of the Earth's oceans, including participation in the Joint Global Ocean Flux Study (JGOFS).

Microwave, both passive and active, and visible/near infrared imaging systems are of particular importance for the study of land surface processes. NERC scientists are currently engaged in a programme to map the land cover of the UK from Landsat Thematic Mapper data, providing information on cover type and habitats vital to the assessment of the state of the environment in Britain. On a larger scale, NERC's Terrestrial Initiative in Global Environmental Research (TIGER) programme integrates remotely sensed data with ground based data to study four important aspects of the interaction between the terrestrial environment and climate. Much of this research is conducted within the context of co-operative programmes such as the International Geosphere-Biosphere Programme (eg in the Global Change and Terrestrial Ecosystems Core Project) or the World Climate Research Programme (eg in the Global Energy and Water Cycle Experiment).

Earth observation systems can collect data from remote and hostile environments, such as the Arctic and Antarctic. They form a key element in polar research as we enter the 21st century. Time series of remotely sensed data now being built up, allow changes in polar environments to be studied. NERC supports UK participation in the remote sensing aspects of major international programmes aimed at better understanding of the processes in the polar regions, such as the Programme for International Polar Ocean Research (PIPOR).

The Earth's atmosphere is of particular current interest. The Universities Global Atmospheric Modelling Programme (UGAMP) takes data from satellite systems designed to investigate the middle and upper atmosphere, concentrating on two main themes: natural variability of the atmosphere and its response to greenhouse forcing; and stratospheric chemistry,

dynamics and prediction of ozone depletion. NERC, through its British Antarctic Survey (BAS), is also responsible for all aspects of Antarctic atmospheric research, and it was BAS scientists who in 1985 first discovered the depletion of Antarctic ozone, now monitored by spaceborne systems.

A key point in all these research areas is the need to combine remotely sensed data with other datasets in integrated models of environmental processes. To this end, the development of integrated geographic information systems (GIS) is another important area of research for NERC; it underpins many applications of Earth observation data. NERC's extensive long term datasets on the marine and terrestrial environments are a key resource in this respect.

NERC is a partner in the British National Space Centre (BNSC), a testimony to its long term commitment to Earth observation in the service of the environmental sciences. Within the BNSC, NERC Scientific Services (NSS) provides the Remote Sensing Applications Development (RSADU) and supports the Dundee Satellite Receiving Station, a facility which has earned a worldwide reputation for excellence in its acquisition, archiving and distribution of imagery in support of scientific programmes. NSS also operates other facilities in support of remote sensing, including a dedicated aircraft equipped with state of the art imaging sensors. Access to other airborne instrumentation is also facilitated by NSS.

Within the context of the BNSC, NERC has sustained, or is currently proposing, a number of initiatives in support of space-related studies. These include funding of ERS-1 Principal Investigators in the UK, support for new applications of ERS-2 data, studies in preparation for the ESA/NASA ARISTOTELES mission and a bid for support of the mission itself. These illustrate the increasing role which observation from space is seen to play in understanding and managing the natural environment.

MARINE SCIENCES.

It has become increasingly clear that any attempt to comprehend the global climate system requires an understanding of the role of the ocean in that system. Currently international programmes such as WOCE and JGOFS are investigating this role. WOCE is looking at the circulation of the ocean, which is important for the transport of heat in the climate system; JGOFS is investigating the biogeochemical fluxes in the ocean, which are important for the carbon dioxide cycle. The major difficulty with any large scale study of the ocean is in obtaining sufficient data, and satellite remote sensing is becoming increasingly important in this area. The global coverage afforded by satellite observations is complementary to the more restricted coverage of *in situ* ship and buoy-based measurements; additionally, the former can only give data about the ocean surface while the latter can provide equally important subsurface data (as well as surface data). Progress is being made by combining data from different satellite instruments with *in situ* data and models, to give a better understanding of the ocean and its role in the climate system.

Much of the work described here is related to aspects of oceanography that require coverage of large geographical areas. Some elements show the utility of remote sensing methods for more localised coastal or biological studies.

Schematic of ERS-1 measuring sea surface topography, showing importance of tracking the satellite accurately.

(courtesy of Rennell Centre)

ERS-1

The launch of the European Space Agency (ESA) ERS-1 satellite on 16 July 1991 was a major step forward for satellite oceanography. This satellite carries a suite of instruments designed to give information primarily about the Earth's oceans and cryosphere. It is the first of a series of satellites (ERS-2, Topex/Poseidon, SeaWiFS) to be launched in the 1990s, primarily to look at the ocean. NERC is funding ESA-selected UK Principal Investigators (PIs), who will use the data from ERS-1 in their research.

There are three major instruments on ERS-1. The radar altimeter gives wind speed, wave height and sea surface topography data. The Active Microwave Instrument (AMI), operates in two modes: the wind scatterometer mode giving wind speed and direction across a 500km swath, and the Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) mode giving a radar image across a 100km swath with a resolution of 25m. The Along Track Scanning Radiometer (ATSR), an infrared radiometer built by the SERC Rutherford Appleton Laboratory, gives precise (to 0.1K) sea surface temperatures across a 500km swath with a resolution of 1km.

Ocean circulation and tides

The first examples use radar altimeter sea surface topography measurements to look at the ocean circulation. The data for these

studies come from the US Navy satellite Geosat, for the period November 1986 to January 1990. From the altimeter topography measurements it is possible to deduce information about the currents in the ocean.

In a recent study Geosat altimeter data have been used to investigate the mesoscale variability of the sea surface topography to the south of South Africa. The variability is a measure of the temporal and spatial unsteadiness of the sea surface, here caused by the Agulhas current flowing south down the east coast of Africa and then retroflecting to flow eastward as the Agulhas Return Current. The eastward flowing Antarctic Circumpolar Current (ACC) lies further to the south of the African continent. The retroflexion causes eddies (the ocean's equivalent to atmospheric depressions, but on a much smaller scale of 100km rather than 1000km) to be shed and the return current to meander downstream of South Africa, in an unsteady manner.

These eddies are important in the transport of heat from the Indian Ocean into the South Atlantic. The information derived from remotely sensed data can be compared with predicted results from the Fine Resolution Antarctic Model (FRAM). Clear similarities can be seen between the Geosat

Variability of sea surface topography (cm) from (left) Geosat altimeter data and (right) the Fine Resolution Antarctic Model (FRAM) in Agulhas Retroflexion region, south of South Africa

(courtesy of RSADU)

First Year Variability

Topography anomaly along the east-west line at 35°N (see above) as a function of time (each tick mark on the vertical axis represents 17 days). Westward propagating features, seen as sloping linear trends in the data, are due to waves caused by the Earth's rotation (planetary waves).

(courtesy of the Rennell Centre)

Amplitude of the M2 tide (cm) in the vicinity of the UK, as calculated from Geosat altimeter data.

(courtesy of Proudman Oceanographic Laboratory)

ERS-1 ATSR data (0.5° resolution) of the Faeroes region, showing temperature change across the Iceland-Faeroes front and eddy features on 22 September 1991. Superimposed triangle shows the area of operation of the RRS Charles Darwin during September 1991.

(Rennell Centre original data courtesy of SERC RAI)

measurements and the FRAM output. The major difference is that the variability is confined to a narrow band in the model, because the eddies produced by the model all travel along the same path, whereas both the Geosat data and *in situ* observations indicate that in reality things are much more variable. Similar analysis has been carried out in the North Atlantic, revealing the effects of the Gulf Stream and planetary waves.

In deriving topographic data from altimetric measurements a correction has to be applied to remove that part of the signal due to the tides. However, it is also possible to use the data to calculate the oceanic tides. In regions where the tides are complex, different tidal corrections to the altimetric data can lead to different estimates of mesoscale variability.

An alternative way of studying ocean circulation is to use visible and infrared images of the sea surface to look at its temperature field. Using successive images, it is possible to examine changes in temperature structure which drive the ocean circulation. Unlike radar measurements, cloud cover prevents visible and infrared sensors viewing the sea surface. By combining the infrared and altimeter data it is possible to gain a better picture of the ocean circulation.

In situ data are also collected to calibrate and validate the remotely sensed information. The NERC vessel, RRS *Charles Darwin*, made oceanographic measurements in September 1991 to obtain data for comparison with ERS-1 altimeter, scatterometer and ATSR data. Measurements made on the cruise encompassed winds and waves, sea surface temperature and salinity, hydrography (that is the subsurface temperature, salinity and density) and currents. These data are being analysed and compared with those acquired by ERS-1 to validate the ERS-1 measurements, a necessary step in their exploitation for oceanographic studies.

ERS-1 scatterometer windfield north of Scotland on 28 November 1991. The red triangle shows the area of operation of the RRS Charles Darwin during the ERS-1 calibration and validation cruise

(courtesy of Rensell Centre/ESA)

Surface fluxes

To understand the circulation of the world's ocean it is important to know the fluxes of momentum, heat and moisture from the atmosphere to the ocean. The surface wind field derived from the ERS-1 scatterometer and ATSR sea surface temperature measurements will contribute to understanding these fluxes. Wind velocity data are necessary for flux calculations and ERS-1 measurements will make a significant impact. This is the first scatterometer flown in space since that on the short lived (three months) NASA Seasat mission in 1978. Similarly, the ATSR will contribute to understanding of the heat fluxes, for which accurate measurements of sea surface temperature are necessary.

The effect of winds on the sea surface temperature is illustrated in the accompanying figure, which shows Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer (AVHRR) data for the Gulf of Tehuantepec (Mexico) for 21 January 1989, from a NOAA (US National Oceanographic and Atmospheric Administration) satellite. Following the onset of a strong offshore wind jet blowing across

The Gulf of Tehuantepec sea surface temperature from AVHRR, together with ship-measured wind vectors. Cooler (green/blue) water due to effect of wind causing mixing of surface waters.

(courtesy of School of Ocean Sciences, University College of North Wales)

the isthmus of Tehuantepec, the sea-surface temperature dropped by approximately 8°C from the previous day, due to intense surface mixing along the axis of the jet. Overplotted is a composite of ship-measured wind vectors, showing the wind jet fanning out over the sea. This example illustrates how, by combining *in situ* and remotely sensed data, changes in air-sea fluxes can be studied.

Biological oceanography

Ocean colour measurements (using the visible part of the electromagnetic spectrum) can give information about the biology of the ocean. It is possible, under certain conditions, to estimate the amount of chlorophyll in the surface water derived from phytoplankton. Currently, no dedicated ocean colour sensor is active, but recently successful use has been made of a visible channel of the AVHRR instrument (which is not optimised for studying biological phenomena) to look at a coccolithophore (a type of phytoplankton)

bloom in the eastern North Atlantic. Data from the AVHRR were received by the NERC Satellite Receiving Station at Dundee University, then sent over the UK academic computer network (JANET) to the NERC Plymouth Marine Laboratory (PML). There the data were processed to give information on the bloom and transmitted to the RRS *Charles Darwin*. With the help of the transmitted images, scientists on board were able to guide the ship to the area of the greatest interest.

With the launch of the ocean colour sensor SeaWiFS in 1993, biological oceanographers will have access to a dedicated tool for more detailed studies of upper ocean biology, which plays an important role in the exchange of carbon dioxide between ocean and atmosphere. NERC scientists made comprehensive use of data from a previous ocean colour mission, the NASA NIMBUS-7 Coastal Zone Colour Scanner (1978-1985), in programmes such as the North Sea Project.

Right AVHRR visible channel data showing a coccolithophore bloom, south of Iceland. This image was transmitted to the RRS Charles Darwin where it was used to guide the vessel to the bloom

(courtesy of PML/NERC Computer Services)

Below Schematic diagram of near real time data acquisition from AVHRR, processing and transmission out to the NERC research vessel RRS Charles Darwin at sea.

Diving behaviour of female elephant seal, tracked by satellite, as it swam from South Georgia to the continental shelf of the Antarctic peninsula, in relation to sea-bed topography (depth in metres). The maximum depth of dive is shown as a brown curtain hanging below the sea surface along the seal's track; viewed from Tierra del Fuego, looking southeast.

(courtesy of SMRU)

A different application of remote sensing in biological oceanography is the use of the ARGOS satellite system to track marine mammals. NERC's Sea Mammal Research Unit has attached satellite transmitters to elephant seals in the South Atlantic. These devices record information about the seals' diving and swimming patterns, with the data being transmitted to the ARGOS satellite, when the seal surfaces, and then back to the UK. One study followed the diving pattern of a female elephant seal as it swam from South Georgia to the continental shelf of the Antarctic peninsula, a distance of some 2600km. The depth of dive is illustrated relative to the bottom topography. The geographical distribution and diving behaviour of the seals are of interest. As predators at the top of the

food chain, the seals play an important role in the Southern Ocean ecosystem and as the most capable divers in the mammalian world, diving to depths of over a mile for more than an hour, they present incomparable challenges to the understanding of mammalian physiology. As undersea predators, able to feed over an enormous range of depths, dive durations and oceanic conditions, they offer opportunities to understand how animals forage in relation to physical and biological oceanography.

Waves

In addition to giving information about sea-surface topography the radar altimeter also provides global measurements of significant wave height. One particular study has looked at the average wave height over the North

Atlantic for three successive winters, measured by the Geosat altimeter. It found that the wave heights increased over that period. This is consistent with a limited number of *in situ* measurements made at weather ships and light vessels, indicating a possible increase in the wave height of the North Atlantic over a period of years. However, data acquired over three years are not adequate to answer the question whether this increase is part of a trend over the whole region, part of a cyclical change on a decadal time scale, or simply due to a shift in the patterns of the winds that generate the waves. With the additional data that will become available over the next few years, from ERS-1, ERS-2 and Topex/Poseidon, it should be possible to answer this question.

Extreme left: Global significant wave measurements (m) from the Geosat altimeter for December 1988 to January 1989 (courtesy of IOSDL/RSADU)

December and January significant wave height measurements (m), from the Geosat altimeter, for the North Atlantic in 1986/7, 1987/8 and 1988/9 (courtesy of IOSDL/RSADU)

Bottom left: Annual average significant wave height (m) as measured over a 25 year period using a shipborne wave recorder on the Seven Stones light vessel (courtesy of IOSDL)

Coastal studies

In addition to the study of large-scale oceanographic phenomena, remote sensing can be used in coastal studies. Two studies of coastal waters around the UK are illustrated here. The first two images show the sea-surface temperature of the North Sea, estimated using the thermal infrared channels of the AVHRR. The data have been corrected for the cooling effect of the atmosphere on the infrared radiation emitted from the sea surface. In addition, the images have been geometrically corrected, to change from a satellite-based coordinate system to an Earth-based coordinate system and also to allow for the geometrical distortion caused by the satellite sensor having an oblique view of the curved surface of the Earth. The resolution of the data is 1km, and the accuracy of the temperature is about 0.2 K.

These relatively cloud free images were selected from the archive of AVHRR data held at the NERC Satellite Receiving Station at Dundee University. They are two of a set of 85 collected during the NERC North Sea Project field campaign (September 1988 to September 1989). The instantaneous structure of the sea-surface temperature can be seen in a way that could not be achieved using ship-based measurements. In an area where the currents are dominated by tides, the detailed patterns change hour by hour as the thermal structure is moved around by the currents. It can be seen that the coastal inshore water tends to be warmer than that offshore, and there appears to be a patch of warm water, probably discharged from the Rhine river. Another interesting feature is the finger-like pattern off the Norfolk coast, which is related to flow over linear sandbanks.

The second example illustrates the use of AVHRR data (from a visible channel) for the Irish Sea. Areas of high backscatter correspond, primarily, to regions of high sediment load in the water column. Strong tidal flows, for example off the west coast of

Anglesey and off the east Irish coast, lead to sediments being mixed from the sea bed into the water column. Similarly estuarine regions can be seen to have a high sediment load. Clearer, less turbid waters are present in the north and where the tidal flows are weaker (for example in North Cardigan Bay). Sequences of such images are being used to try to relate changes in sediment distribution to the underlying tidal flows.

Two AVHRR infrared sea surface temperature images of the North Sea.

(courtesy of Department of Oceanography, Southampton University)

The MAHLOVS project

An illustration of the integrated approach which needs to be taken in understanding the physical and biological processes in the ocean is the Middle and High Latitude Ocean Variability Study (MAHLOVS), part of the NASA Eos interdisciplinary programme. Proposed and conducted by a team of NERC-supported scientists, the project will link satellite measurements of atmospheric forcing of the ocean, and the consequent oceanic response, with the biological productivity determined from ocean colour sensors.

AVHRR visible channel data for the Irish Sea, for which high backscatter corresponds primarily to high sediment load in the water column.

(courtesy of School of Ocean Sciences, UCNW)

•EARTH SCIENCES.

Earth sciences was one of the first disciplines to make use of remotely sensed data. A wide variety of research topics and practical applications are currently being investigated by NERC-supported scientists. These range from observation of major structural features of continental scale to the definition of areas of economic potential of a few hundred metres square. This research is mainly undertaken by the NERC British Geological Survey, but work is also supported in higher education institutions in the UK.

The primary data source for many Earth science applications is the Landsat Thematic Mapper (TM). Information is available covering large areas, but with limited spectral capabilities and is used primarily for regional-scale structural mapping worldwide.

More recent instruments, presently confined to airborne platforms, provide limited spatial coverage, but with extended spectral capabilities in the visible, near infrared and thermal infrared regions of the spectrum. These have been successfully used for mineralogical identification and lithological discrimination in areas of economic potential.

Structural mapping

An early and continuing use of TM data has been to provide large scale, structural overviews of areas of interest. A typical TM scene covers an area of 185 x 185km. Regional-scale structures, including major faults and folds and large scale geomorphological features, can be clearly observed. TM data have been used in arid terrains to define major fault structures, which may affect the hydrology of the area, providing drilling targets to explore for groundwater supplies. In the UK, major structural features and glacial geomorphology can be clearly seen. Combined with Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) they provide a suitable 3-D base for construction projects.

This spectacular Thematic Mapper image of the Lake District has yielded important information on both its solid and superficial geology. The extent of glacial features, such as drumlin fields produced during the last Ice Age, are unusually clear.

(courtesy of the British Geological Survey)

Large scale structural mapping projects are currently being undertaken by NERC scientists in several countries as an aid to exploration for economic mineral resources. Techniques are being developed to map the distribution of subsurface geological units, based on their surface exposure, combined with surface structural mapping and a DEM.

Mineralogical mapping and lithological discrimination

TM data also have a role in defining large scale variations in lithology and ground cover. Although the TM instrument has limited spectral capabilities, it can be used to highlight regions of interest based on gross spectral differences, such as those between vegetation and background lithology and between highly altered areas and background lithology in areas of economic mineralisation. This has been clearly shown for areas of copper mineralisation in Peru and gold mineralisation in Egypt. However, for detailed mineral mapping the TM data remain too insensitive.

Airborne platforms carrying advanced high spectral resolution instruments have provided a new source of data, currently being investigated for a variety of applications in Europe and the US. These instruments give very fine spectral detail which, used in conjunction with a library of mineral spectra, provides a means of identifying the dominant mineralogy of the surface components. The most active application is in mineral exploration. The effectiveness of this approach is currently being tested in the US, Australia and Spain at sites supported through NERC. Work has concentrated on developing techniques to match spectra from airborne instruments with the corresponding library spectra. Concurrent research to deal with the mixed spectral signatures of surface mineral components has also been carried out. The results from mixture decomposition, combined with the use of passive thermal imagery, may provide a route to lithological identification and hence automatic geological mapping of the Earth's surface.

Hazard monitoring

A further application is in hazard monitoring. Research into the thermal regimes of active volcanoes using a variety of sensors (including TM and NASA's AVIRIS system), suggests that monitoring heat flux of volcanoes is feasible. Large changes in these fluxes may signal an eruptive event. This information, combined with simulations of flow events from a crater using a DEM produced from stereo pairs (derived from SPOT image pairs), provides a means of risk assessment.

Solid Earth science

ARISTOTELES, a joint ESA/NASA mission due for launch in 1997, will provide for the first time accurate, global information on the Earth's gravity and magnetic fields. It aims to

map the shape of the geoid to an accuracy of 3cm. Precision of this order will allow study of how mantle motions are coupled to the lithosphere and how the lithosphere responds to forces acting on it. The data will also be invaluable in the study of tectonic processes, continental deformation and vulcanism.

Studies on the Earth's magnetic field will provide information on the core field and its secular variations, relevant to studies of fluid motions in the Earth's core and of the dynamo which drives the field. Accurate models of these geomagnetic effects are also needed for navigational purposes.

Improved knowledge of the geoid will enable the measurement of departures of the sea surface from the geoid, caused by ocean currents. This information is vital for understanding the transport of heat and momentum in the oceans.

NERC has recently supported a preliminary programme to investigate the better utilisation of ARISTOTELES data and will be responsible for UK support of the mission within ESA.

Comparison of spectra from an airborne sensor and a library of mineral spectra. The shape and position of the major absorptions of the airborne spectrum (blue) correspond to those of the library spectrum of muscovite (yellow), which in this case is associated with gold mineralisation.

(courtesy of RSADU)

Digital elevation models of the surface topography of the volcano Soufriere Hills in Montserrat, West Indies, are used to show how future eruptions would threaten communities living on the volcano. The zones green through purple show areas of increasing hazard superimposed on a shaded relief image of the topography and the settlement pattern.

(courtesy of the NERC Unit for Thematic Information Systems (NUTIS))

•POLAR SCIENCES.

Satellite systems provide an important means of studying polar regions. Especially important are the microwave sensors of the type carried by, amongst others, the ERS-1 satellite. With their ability to penetrate cloud, these systems are capable of providing valuable information on ice sheet mass balance, sea ice extent and type and the morphology of glaciers and ice sheets. Recent evidence has also shown that multiple frequency Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) systems can differentiate very subtle distinctions in sea ice type and age. These topics are also critically important to understanding of the processes which contribute to, and in turn are affected by, climate change.

NERC's British Antarctic Survey conducts a wide range of research in Antarctica and the surrounding seas, including the study of ecosystems, meteorology, geophysics and ice chemistry and dynamics. Further research is supported through university groups, primarily at the Scott Polar Research Institute (SPRI), and the Mullard Space Science Laboratory (MSSL).

Polar regions and climate

The polar regions have a strong influence on the Earth's climate. Transfer of heat and momentum between the atmosphere and the oceans is restricted in the polar seas, where ice cover acts as an insulating blanket: changes in the extent of this blanket are critical in modulating circulation processes.

Melting and freezing of polar sea ice affects the processes of deep water formation which are critical in transferring carbon dioxide from the atmosphere to the deep ocean, where it is removed from the climate system. In terms of the potential effects of climate change, if the vast ice sheets of Greenland and Antarctica were to melt, the level of the Earth's oceans would be raised by about 60 metres.

Less dramatic, but also very important, is the potential release of methane from the Arctic permafrost due to increased temperatures. Methane is 21 times more effective, molecule for molecule, as a greenhouse gas than carbon dioxide and its release could lead to amplification of global warming. Changes in the reflectance, or albedo, of the ice sheets and snowfields of the poles also have a dramatic effect on the radiation balance of the Earth.

Ice sheet mass balance

Ice sheets are formed over the polar landmasses (as opposed to ice *shelves*, which are formed over the open sea). The two great ice sheets, those of Greenland and the Antarctic, together hold over 90% of the Earth's freshwater. Their thickness is constantly changing as ice is redistributed within the sheet. This leads to a process whereby snowfall forms ice on the central plateaux which is then balanced by loss at the coastal region in the formation of ice

shelves and calving of icebergs. This process may take many thousands of years, during which the sheet builds up a climatic record which can only be interpreted through a knowledge of ice sheet dynamics.

Radar altimeter data are critically important in providing very precise, repeated measures of the topography of the great ice sheets. These data will provide us with the answer to a fundamental question which is still unresolved after 25 years of fieldwork, namely, are the ice sheets shrinking or growing? If they are shrinking, this could provide one of the most sensitive indicators of global climate change. A composite of over two million measurements made with the Geosat altimeter over the Antarctic ice sheet reveals surface flow features and reflects the underlying topography of the Antarctic landmass. ERS-1 data, reaching to 82°S (compared with the 72°S limit of Geosat) will provide much better coverage of Antarctica.

Synthetic Aperture Radar image of the Greenland Ice Sheet, showing crevasses used for tracking ice motion and a number of outlet glaciers

(courtesy of Jet Propulsion Laboratory (JPL)/SPRI)

NERC supports UK research groups in the international Polar Ice Sheet Programme (PISP), involving 23 countries, which constitutes the largest ever comprehensive research study of the polar ice sheets. This programme will use altimeter, SAR and ATSR data to measure all elements of ice sheet mass balance. This work has been funded as part of a NERC Special Topic research programme in support of ERS-1 Principal Investigators in the UK.

Ice shelf processes

Ice shelves form a second flow regime for ice in the polar regions. As ice streams and glaciers reach the edge of the land mass, ice shelves extending hundreds of kilometres into the ocean may be formed.

These shelves can be subject to catastrophic changes, some examples of which shown in the accompanying figures. The Wordie ice shelf lies off the Western side of the Antarctic peninsula. Over 10-15 years the ice shelf has undergone a rapid disintegration as a result of a rise in mean air temperatures. The resulting increased amounts of meltwater, combined with underlying fracture processes, have led to the breaking up of the shelf.

An even more dramatic event occurred in 1985/86 at the periphery of the much larger Larsen ice shelf, the most northerly of the Antarctic peninsula. The sequence of 3-D views of the ice shelf from Geosat altimeter data from 1985 to 1986 show that the large promontory (A) in the previous figure, well known for over 40 years, has become detached as an enormous tabular iceberg, roughly the size of East Anglia and weighing one thousand billion tonnes. This single event was equivalent to the total annual loss of ice from Antarctica through a normal summer. The iceberg is slowly melting, as shown from altimeter measurements of its freeboard; it is also being tracked by other satellite sensors.

The disintegration of the Wordie ice shelf as a result of rising air temperatures in the Antarctic is seen here in a sequence of Landsat images. (courtesy of British Antarctic Survey)

Contour map of the Larsen Ice Shelf derived from Seasat altimeter data. The inflow from ice feeder streams is clearly visible. The location of grounding points and surface rifts are indicated.

(courtesy of MSSLI)

Sequence derived from Geosat altimeter data showing the calving of an iceberg, roughly the size of East Anglia and weighing one thousand billion tonnes. The loss of ice through this single event is of the same order as estimates of the annual ice loss from the entire Antarctic periphery. (courtesy of MSSLI)

Sea ice

Sea ice plays an important role in substantially modifying interactions between the ocean and the atmosphere. The presence of ice disrupts the normal exchange of energy and momentum between the two fluids and can have a very significant effect on climate by effectively insulating the sea from the cold atmosphere. Furthermore, the melting and freezing of sea ice dominates the mixed layer dynamics, and therefore the vertical structure of the upper ocean. This has consequences in terms of ocean circulation and the ability of the oceans to remove carbon dioxide from the atmosphere.

The extent, age and to some degree thickness of sea ice can be determined using data from a range of remote sensing systems. Altimeter data and passive microwave imagers can map the extent of ice cover, the two techniques providing cross checks and validation of results. SAR and other active imaging systems can provide information on the age of sea ice and its type; these important factors substantially modify the influence of the ice.

Individual ice floes, re-imaged every three days with the ERS-1 SAR, can be tracked to allow the circulation of the surface waters to be studied. The independence of microwave systems, with respect to cloud cover and ability to operate without solar illumination, make them particularly valuable during the poor weather frequently encountered in the long polar winters.

The annual growth and decay of Antarctic sea ice (Feb 1987 to Feb 1988) as observed using the Geosat altimeter. The data complement established passive microwave satellite observations

(courtesy of MSSL)

The Scoresby Programme

Led by the Scott Polar Research Institute, an international consortium has proposed a major programme of marine research in the Nordic seas to be carried out in 1993. Named in honour of William Scoresby, an early pioneer of polar and oceanographic research, the programme aims to study the physical, chemical, acoustical and biological properties of the ocean in the region of the ice edge. The work will be carried out in the Odden region and in the marginal ice zone of the Greenland Sea. Satellite microwave

sensors will be used to measure ice extent and type. Data from the SeaWiFS ocean colour sensor and airborne laser fluorescence systems will be used to study the primary productivity of the Greenland Sea, which plays a crucial role in drawdown of carbon dioxide from the atmosphere. The rate of drawdown is linked directly to ocean dynamics, which in turn depends on the behaviour of sea ice. Research cruises and other forms of data gathering will take place along with satellite data acquisition.

ATMOSPHERIC SCIENCES.

NERC shares, with the UK Meteorological Office and the Science and Engineering Research Council (SERC), the responsibility for supporting research in the atmospheric sciences. NERC sustains a broad capability in atmospheric research by promoting work primarily on the non-ionised, lower regions of the atmosphere and its interactions with the Earth's surface. This work is carried out in a number of UK universities and polytechnics. In addition, the unique facilities of NERC's British Antarctic Survey (BAS) support research on the ionised upper reaches of the atmosphere.

Satellite-borne instruments, developed primarily by (in the UK) SERC-supported scientists, will provide information to be incorporated in models of the chemical, physical and dynamic processes in the atmosphere. Furthermore, Earth observation systems will be important in driving models of surface processes which govern the fluxes of energy, momentum and chemical constituents between the biosphere and the atmosphere.

NERC support for university and institute research into the use of satellite data, primarily thermal and passive microwave imagery, for rainfall monitoring and forecasting, complements the work of the Met Office in this area.

Air-surface interactions

A high priority in climate research is understanding the transfer of energy and momentum between the atmosphere and elements of the Earth's surface: water, soil, rock, vegetation, ice or snow. With the wide range of scientific disciplines at its disposal NERC is uniquely placed to carry out research into the transfer mechanisms between the components of the climate system. The contribution to be made by remote sensing in this area, for example, in air-sea interactions or through study of carbon dioxide drawdown processes in the terrestrial biosphere, are described elsewhere, illustrating the interdisciplinary nature of the science.

Polar Meteorology

Both polar regions provide increasingly important natural laboratories for atmospheric sciences. BAS carries out research in every part of the Antarctic atmosphere, from its interaction with the surface through the ionised upper atmosphere and its interaction with space. Satellite observations are particularly important at the poles, where local information is difficult to collect. Snow accumulation rates, derived from passive microwave sensors, are important in calculating ice sheet mass balance, while AVHRR imagery is used to estimate wind vectors by tracking clouds. The thermal structure of mesoscale systems is also investigated through temperature measurements from satellites.

Passive microwave data from the SSM/I for the Antarctic region acquired on 1 October 1987. Areas of precipitation are shown in red, together with sea ice and low cloud (yellow) and open water and cold inland ice (blue).

(courtesy of BAS)

To understand the carbon cycle, exchange of carbon dioxide between the atmosphere and the oceans, land surface and cryosphere need to be understood, calling for an interdisciplinary approach.

The annual depletion of ozone above the Antarctic, discovered by BAS scientists in 1985, is clearly seen here in a NIMBUS-7 map of ozone distribution.

(courtesy of NASA)

Atmospheric chemistry and global models

The atmosphere is a particularly sensitive indicator of chemical processes. Discoveries, such as the Antarctic ozone 'hole' in 1985 by BAS scientists, have shown how little we understand basic atmospheric chemistry and interactions with dynamical and physical processes.

Many local environmental problems can only be addressed properly within a global perspective. A major priority is to develop global atmospheric circulation models and to analyse and interpret their output. The Universities Global Atmospheric Modelling Programme (UGAMP) models the interactions between dynamical, radiative and chemical processes in the atmosphere. UGAMP concentrates on two main themes: natural variability of the atmosphere and its responses to atmospheric forcing; and stratospheric chemistry, dynamics and prediction of ozone depletion. Data from the Upper Atmosphere Research Satellite (UARS) on the chemistry of the upper atmosphere will provide a vital input into these models. The microwave limb sounder on UARS was developed by a group including the Jet Propulsion Laboratory, SERC Rutherford Appleton Laboratory and the Departments of Physics at Heriot Watt University and Meteorology at Edinburgh University. NERC supports analysis at Edinburgh which receives the satellite data daily from JPL via a dedicated computer link.

Models of atmospheric flow will incorporate remotely sensed data with information from other sources.

The distribution of water vapour and ozone at an altitude of 26km in the southern hemisphere on 8 November 1991. Data acquired from the Microwave Limb Sounder on UARS.

(courtesy of SERC RAL/JPL/Heriot-Watt & Edinburgh Universities)

Remote Sensing of Land Surface Processes

An increased understanding of ecosystem interactions with the atmosphere, and hence climate, is necessary for accurate monitoring of global climate change. Initial work in the USA has indicated that this requirement may be met by using regional ecosystem models driven by climatic (rainfall, temperature) and vegetation (leaf area index, nutrient status) information obtained from remotely sensed data. The provision of accurate information on vegetation status, however, depends on an understanding of how radiation interacts with a vegetation canopy. It requires the development of invertible models linking canopy characteristics with remotely sensed spectral properties. By sponsoring university and collaborative research, NERC is addressing these issues through its Terrestrial Initiative in Global Environmental Research (TIGER).

TIGER

TIGER is a major NERC research programme with four main foci, comprising carbon cycling on the land, trace greenhouse gas fluxes, land surface water and energy balance and the impacts of climate change on ecosystems. These themes address specific gaps in knowledge. For example, carbon cycling is fundamental to biosphere operation but little is known about the magnitude and timing of carbon movement through the soil-plant system. Similarly, the circulation of methane and nitrous oxide, which may account for one fifth of greenhouse heating, is poorly understood. Detailed information on the partitioning of incoming solar radiation in the water and energy balance is required for the major biomes of the world. The final component of TIGER is to develop a capacity to predict the biological, ecological and physical effects of climate change on terrestrial ecosystems at patch, landscape and biome scales. Earth observation data will feature in projects in TIGER themes I, III and IV.

Images of a Forestry Commission plantation near Thetford, East Anglia, acquired by the Jet Propulsion Laboratory (JPL) multi-frequency, multi-polarisation SAR. Each image represents the radar backscatter from the forest for a particular combination of transmitted and received linear polarisations, with the response of each frequency in red, green and blue.

(courtesy of RSADU)

TIGER I: Carbon Cycling on the Land

Tropical rainforests are a key component of the terrestrial carbon cycle. Information on the current state and temporal evolution of tropical rainforests is an important requirement in global climate research. SAR will provide information on forest extent and condition, to estimate biomass and begin to map by species of tree, growth stage and possibly health. The ideal multi-polarisation, multi-frequency sensors are not currently available on satellite platforms. The present work, therefore, involves the development of models of backscatter from airborne and low orbit campaigns in the UK with American and Canadian multi-frequency radars. These models will be used to aid monitoring in Brazil and West Africa by the current generation of single frequency orbiting radars (on the Almaz, ERS-1 and JERS-1 satellites).

TIGER III: Land Surface Water and Energy Balance

Under the World Climate Research Programme several universities and NERC institutes are involved in the second of a series of international field experiments to study the energy and water budget of the land surface. The Hydrological Atmospheric Pilot Experiment (HAPEX) approach is to measure the energy balance of all the principal vegetation types within an area equivalent to a Global Circulation Model (GCM) grid square. A comprehensive ground data collection programme in the Sahel region of West Africa will obtain measurements of evaporation, sensible heat flux, radiation balance and surface temperature from three contrasting Sahelian land cover types. These data will be used to calibrate and correct remotely sensed data to make regional estimates of evaporation. A critical phase of the work will be determination of the effect of atmospheric variation and the variability of ground cover reflectance on the remotely sensed signal. This will involve measurement of the bi-directional reflectance distribution function (BRDF) of vegetation and retrieval of atmospheric optical variables. Both these elements affect the accurate estimation of the regional surface radiation budget and hence regional estimation of surface evaporation.

The HAPEX-Sahel test site showing the location of three intensively monitored 'super sites'

(courtesy of Institute of Hydrology)

The extrapolation of ground measurements to satellite altitudes is an extension of research undertaken by NERC's Institute of Hydrology (IH) as part of the First International Satellite Land Surface Climatology Project (ISLSCP) Field Experiment (FIFE). This multi-national, multi-disciplinary study of the Konza Prairie, Kansas involved IH in extending point measurements of temperature, energy, momentum and carbon dioxide fluxes over large areas, using remotely sensed data. In common with HAPEX, IH will also be applying these approaches in the forthcoming Boreal Ecosystem Atmosphere Study (BOREAS) and Global Energy and Water Cycle Experiment (GEWEX) programmes.

TIGER IV: The Impact of Climate Change on Ecosystems

Changes in the extent and geographical disposition of biomes have important consequences for natural resources and for the likely effects on biodiversity and on the functioning of global ecosystems. Large scale changes in terrestrial ecosystems are likely to influence Earth system processes and may modify many of the driving variables in GCMs. Remotely sensed and ground based data will be combined in integrated models of ecosystem behaviour to help understand and predict the likely consequences of climate change on terrestrial ecosystems. The repetitive monitoring capability of satellite sensors will also provide an indication of turnover in biomes to condition mechanistic models of biome adaptation.

The Llyn Brianne experiment comprised deployment of seven sensors over two months:
 a) NASA ER-2 carried the Airborne Visible and InfraRed Imaging Spectrometer (AVIRIS) (courtesy of NASA Ames Research Centre)
 b) false colour composite acquired by the Compact Airborne Spectrographic Imager (CASI) (courtesy of RSADU)

c) Spectron SE-590 data acquired from a helicopter (courtesy of University of Salford)

Plant physics and biochemistry

Important remote sensing research directed at a clearer understanding of the interaction of light with plant canopies is being undertaken outside TIGER. High spectral resolution remotely sensed data are being used in a large project in northern Florida. Estimates of forest leaf area index and canopy nutrient status from these data will be used in a labile carbon model to derive net primary productivity (NPP). Similarly, UK and US scientists have been testing hypotheses derived from the NASA-funded Oregon Transect Ecosystem Research (OTTER) project, at Llyn Brianne, Central

Wales. This is part of the European deployment of NASA experimental sensors, including AVIRIS and the AirSAR. The aim of the work is the same as in Florida, but the near simultaneous collection of a number of airborne data sets with supporting ground data will allow synergistic use of these data to condition the scale dependence of the links between reflectance and plant biophysics and biochemistry.

Further research is examining the 3-D geometry of the reflecting surface and its directional reflectance properties. This will extend the value of traditional spectral and temporal measures of reflectance. The emphasis is on developing models of surface scattering which can be inverted to infer fundamental, physical properties of the surface for example, leaf angle distribution in vegetation canopies from sample measurements of directional reflectance. This research has also shown that it is possible to obtain an improved estimate of Earth surface albedo from off-nadir measurements.

A sparse angular sample of directional reflectance measurements is used, in combination with a physical model of surface scattering, to infer the hemispherical reflectance and hence the albedo of the surface

(courtesy of University College London)

Remote Sensing and Geographic Information Systems

Products from remotely sensed data are increasingly seen as key components in geographic information systems. A particular interest has been the production of regional and national land cover maps. Techniques are also being developed for analysing data along with information contained in GIS environments. The following are examples of the range of this research.

Mapping the land cover of Great Britain

The last detailed land cover map of Great Britain was generated in the early 1960s by ground-based survey. In contrast, in the 1990s, the land cover is being derived by multi-temporal classification of red, near infrared and middle infrared bands of summer and winter imagery acquired by the Landsat Thematic Mapper (TM). Twenty five target classes will be mapped consistently throughout Britain, while for any one area a hierarchical stratification allows further discrimination of cover types. Accuracy is assessed by direct comparison with a stratified random sample of the NERC Institute of Terrestrial Ecology (ITE) Countryside Survey 1990. This dataset comprises land class data, quadrat information on the cover of individual plant species, linear and point features. The final land cover map will be a component in the ITE National Geographical Information System on Environment (NGISE) along with, for example, topographic, soils and geological maps and the detailed grid-referenced species data of the Biological Records Centre.

Determining urban land use from high spatial resolution remotely-sensed images

NERC collaborates on the exploitation of remotely sensed information through joint programmes with other Research Councils,

A composite of four areas taken from the land cover mapping programme based on Landsat TM imagery:

- i) London
- ii) River Bure, Norfolk
- iii) Medway Estuary
- iv) North York Moors

(courtesy of ITE, Environmental Information Centre (EIC))

Classification of land use in a SPOT-HRV multispectral image of part of the London Borough of Bromley obtained using

- a) a conventional, per-pixel algorithm (left)
- b) a spatial re-classification algorithm (below)

(courtesy of University College London and South East Regional Research Laboratory)

for example in urban area analysis. Conventional, per-pixel multispectral classifications of urban areas tend to yield relatively low levels of accuracy, because they are complex spatial assemblages of many different land cover types (eg buildings, tarmac, trees, grass). Under the NERC/ Economic and Social Research

Council (ESRC) programme on Geographical Data Handling, spatial or contextual re-classifiers have been developed. These examine the spatial arrangement of a set of broad land-cover types present within the scenes, determined by a low-level segmentation of the image. Object-based techniques are being

developed which group adjacent pixels with an identical land cover (class) label into a single object and encode the spatial (topological) relationships between all of the objects within the scene. These facets are then employed to derive land use.

Land cover monitoring in a GIS framework

The traditional method of image classification tends to be based purely on the spectral values of individual pixels. The spatial and temporal context of such spectral differences can be equally valuable for land cover monitoring. One alternative to traditional classification involves using a knowledge base of contextual information, for example cartographic data, which can serve as a rule model for the image segmentation. Such a system will, for example, allow the structural-functional components of a landscape (eg forestry,

agricultural land, semi-natural areas) to be characterised so they are compatible with, and useful in, field surveys. Use of the geometric properties of agricultural landscapes to constrain the image segmentation is the most obvious example. The approach will be particularly valuable where the boundaries between different land parcels may be indistinct and the change in cover types gradual. The segmentation rule model is then based, for example, on ecological variables.

Tropical deforestation monitoring

Information on the extent and rate of tropical forest clearance and quantitative estimates of forest regrowth are required for planning global environmental policy. Methodologies for forest monitoring in Amazonia are being developed in collaboration with the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP). Estimates of forest and non-forest area have

Several AVHRR images, covering the entire Amazon Basin were classified and geo-corrected to form a single digital map showing forest cover. This detail, from Rondonia, shows the forest map derived from AVHRR after integration with other geographically referenced datasets within an ARC/INFO GIS

(courtesy of NUTIS)

been derived from data acquired by the Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer (AVHRR) sensor and found to be consistent with those from higher spatial and spectral resolution satellite sensors. Forest regrowth models are now being used to improve the delimitation of secondary regrowth and undisturbed forest. The rate of deforestation is also being derived using multi-temporal AVHRR datasets. At test sites in Brazil, where extensive deforestation is known to have occurred, the processing methodology has been established using image texture and edge detection of these multi-temporal data. The resultant maps were subsequently incorporated into a GIS to investigate the factors controlling deforestation.

Interpolation of remotely sensed data for vegetation monitoring

Multi-temporal approaches are being used in Europe for monitoring agricultural yields. High spatial resolution data are used to identify homogenous crop areas and then temporal profiles of the Normalised Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), derived from AVHRR data, are extracted from them.

Example of an early implementation of segmentation software. White lines within heath areas (green and brown tones) reflect ecologically meaningful boundaries.

(courtesy of NUTIS and EIC)

At a test site in Greece the NVDVI data were integrated over the growing season for each crop to estimate the crop area and yield of wheat, rice, maize and cotton. The estimates, derived from remotely sensed data alone, were found to be within 90% of the official statistics except for wheat. In this case while NDVI was useful for the germination and vegetative stages of wheat, input from a simple agro-meteorological model was found to be necessary to detect a good grain-filling period.

Remote sensing in the Less Favoured Areas: models for rural land use planning

The ability to map and monitor changes in rural land use is a key component of the EEC programme on Less Favoured Areas of the Community. The information supplied by remotely sensed data constitutes one layer in a planning information system for land management. An integrated digital data base for the Snowdonia National Park has been constructed which includes land cover maps derived from Landsat TM and SPOT HRV imagery and elevation data. The data are used to aid land management decisions, for example to assess the environmental impacts of sea level rise, afforestation or reservoir expansion.

Freshwater Hydrology

Remote sensing techniques have considerable potential in freshwater hydrology. Sensors can provide information on soil moisture, on the distribution of pervious surfaces for run-off modelling, for assessment of water quality and for mapping the surface characteristics of rivers and lakes.

Soil moisture

Water availability can determine the distribution of plant species and for most green plants a marked change in optical reflectance results from stressing due to water shortage. The effect of water supply

on vegetation can, therefore, be used as an indicator of moisture change. The surface temperature is also related to soil moisture since wet surfaces have a higher thermal capacity than dry ones and are cooler during the day and warmer at night. Most applications of thermal mapping have looked at vegetated surfaces to relate evaporation rates to available soil moisture. IH is using these approaches to map regional evaporation rates in Kansas and the Sahel. In addition, radar can monitor soil moisture changes because the backscattered signal is related to the electrical properties of soil. Repetitive monitoring enables soil moisture changes to be studied whilst unwanted effects, for example surface roughness, are reduced. Ground-based experiments, such as those being undertaken by IH in the Sahel, and at Halvergate Marshes as part of the MAESTRO campaign, will determine the utility of radar data in soil moisture determination. Such development forms an important part of the IH ERS-1 Special Topic studies.

Areal estimates of roofs (red), roads (black) and pervious (green) surfaces obtained from Airborne Thematic Mapper (ATM) imagery for input into the WASSP run-off model

(courtesy of IH)

Run-off modelling

Catchment response to rainfall changes with urbanisation or the development of frozen ground. Prediction of the response requires models to calculate surface run-off for a given rainfall intensity and duration. The percentage of impervious surface within the catchment and its variation with temperature are key inputs to such models. Remotely sensed data can be used to assess the percentage of impervious surface, by

Evaporation derived from Landsat satellite data, over a 15 x15km area of West Africa highest evaporation from the river, lowest from harvested fields

(courtesy of IH)

classification of the land cover, and to monitor the variation in surface temperature of the land. For example, IH used remotely sensed data to differentiate between vegetated and non-vegetated surfaces in nine catchments contributing flow to individual drains in a trunk sewer at Kidlington, Oxford. These components were classified to give areal estimates of each vegetation type and the areas of roof, roads and paths for input into the WASSP run-off model. IH is also using calibrated thermal infrared data from the AVHRR sensor to derive the extent of frozen ground for input into models of catchment streamflow response. Similarly both NOAA AVHRR and ERS-1 SAR data are being used by University of Bristol for estimating snow area and snow pack parameters in Europe.

Water quality

Remote sensing has been widely used in studying lake water quality. The reflectance characteristics of inland waters are determined by three optically important components: dissolved organic carbon (DOC), suspended mineral particles and the concentration of phytoplankton chlorophyll. Clear water has a relatively simple spectral signature, decreasing rapidly with increasing wavelength to zero above 700nm. The systematic addition of DOC decreases reflectance at wavelengths below 600nm. Most suspended minerals increase reflectance over a relatively broad range of wavelengths while phytoplankton decreases the reflectance of water at wavelengths below 500nm and can produce definite reflectance peaks at wavelengths between 550nm and 600nm. Remotely sensed data acquired by imaging spectrometers have been used to examine the effects of land use on the productivity of lakes in the English Lake District. The summer chlorophyll maximum was clearly observed in all the lakes, but this was associated with blue-green algae in the more productive lakes and a variety of small flagellates in more impoverished waters.

Flow patterns in inland waters

The transient nature of wind-induced flow patterns in lakes is particularly suited to analysis by airborne remote sensing techniques. For example, in a study of Esthwaite Water, Cumbria, the NERC Institute of Freshwater Ecology (IFE) monitored the dispersion of simple floating targets, which are highly reflective in the near infrared, by repeatedly flying over the lake. The trajectories of the surface currents were inferred from the position of the targets and the results used to validate a 3-D numerical model of the wind-induced flow. Similarly remote sensing can be used to validate models of pollutant dispersion in river channels. The retention times of pollutants within a particular river reach are a function of the formation and destruction of local patches of slow-moving water in well-

Water temperature variations in a 'dead zone' in the River Severn obtained from thermal ATM imagery

(courtesy of IFE)

The height profile of the Amazon river derived from 17 days of Seasat altimeter data. Regular monitoring with ERS-1 is expected to show seasonal and inter-annual variations in the river flow.

(courtesy of MSSL)

developed pools and meanders. These 'dead zones' delay the downstream transport of solutes, fine particles and planktonic algae. IFE has used airborne techniques to study the formation and dissolution of dead zones in the River Severn, allowing observation of the structure of their eddies and their boundaries with the main flow.

Height profiling and water area monitoring

The first synoptic water level profile of a large part of the Amazon river has been derived from Seasat altimeter data, to a precision of 30cm. The availability of altimeter data from the ERS-1 satellite will allow production of a series of synoptic profiles for comparison with the Seasat data and for monitoring water level changes with season. Similarly altimeter data can be used to derive lake water level which, used in tandem with lake surface area derived from AVHRR imagery, provides an estimate of lake volume. ATSR and altimeter data from ERS-1 will be used to monitor the lake volumes of 500 globally distributed lakes.

.ENDWORD.

This brochure has shown the wide range of research being carried out through Earth observation under the auspices of the UK Natural Environment Research Council.

Over the next decade many satellites are due to be launched carrying new sensors for observing the Earth. This will lead to an order of magnitude increase in the amount of data available to environmental scientists.

As a result, the coming years will present both new challenges and new opportunities for understanding the Earth's environment from space.

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